

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: VELÁZQUEZ****FIRST NAME: ENRIQUE****PROGRAM CODE: DDIA****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: PROF. GULMA**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did *not* use Grammarly Premium

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: xx%

The author used Word for Microsoft 365 on Windows 11 64-bit

Six key concepts in this response paper

1. Academic essays (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 7)
2. Starting the essay (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 7)
3. Writing the essay (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 10)
4. Achieving “Logical Flow” (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 39)
5. Signal phrases (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 38)
6. Avoiding plagiarism (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 34)

ACADEMIC WRITING ESSENTIALS

1) INTRODUCTION

Writing an academic essay can be a daunting task, even for an experienced writer familiar with the structures and shared foundations of similar crafts. For those not accustomed to writing, the prospect of expanding into academic writing can appear monumentally challenging. The “Academic Writing Essentials” extrapolates six main ideas from “ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1.” In this work, Cleenewerck and Gulma demystify academic writing for those unfamiliar with these core concepts. This response paper extrapolates key elements in Cleenewerck and Gulma to distill the knowledge attainment for the reader. First, the reader will receive a primer on what academic writing is – what is and how it differs from nonacademic writing. This forms the basis for starting on the journey of academic writing. Aspirant academic researchers need to understand the *why* behind a decision. The *why* behind academic writing is no different. Second, the reader flows through how to start on the writing journey, which is a literary, not literal, journey through words beginning with a plan. A failure to plan is indeed a plan to fail for most. The plan is the genesis for writing, the framework, and the blueprint needed to progress successfully and efficiently to completion. Third, the reader learns about the writing building blocks, and the structure, which will develop out of words and concepts. Fourth, the reader will progress through establishing a logical flow to the written words that allows them to connect with the readers so that the reader may imbibe the core concepts

and walk away more knowledgeable or with thought-provoking ideas that challenge their own beliefs, the core of academic writing. Fifth, the reader will learn what signal phrases are and how to utilize them effectively to reaffirm two core tenets – maintaining engagement with the reader and giving credit to the author who contributed to the furtherance of the writer’s research. Lastly, the reader will explore what plagiarism is, why it is something to avoid, and how to give the author proper credit for their intellectual property. The journey is long, though; the fruits will be worth the effort when the academic researcher follows the proven formula for success.

2) ACADEMIC ESSAYS

While the section on academic essays is brief in relation to the other essential elements highlighted in ACA-401/ACA401D coursepack 1, a solid foundation cannot progress without first noting the differences between academic and non-academic writing. What distinguishes academic from non-academic writing is the purpose. Central to the core, academic essays propose a hypothesis and, like any good scientific research, seek to answer the question presented (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 7). In short, what I learned is that academic essays are a search for truth through reasoned research and conclusions supported by evidence (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 7). Nonacademic essays, by contrast, do not adhere to the same standard in that while these mediums may search for truth, they do not seek to advance research to do so.

3) STARTING THE ESSAY

As critical as it is to understand what an academic essay is, planning will rue the day, as is evidenced by the lateness in submitting my own response paper. Writing an academic essay is a monumental undertaking. One that requires planning; defining a question early on and then finding thematical content that allows for the essay to flow organically (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 7). Cleenewerck & Gulma astutely note which elements to incorporate into that initial plan, inclusive of an outline, initial thoughts on the source materials and milestones that shape the trajectory of the research essay (7). Like charting a course, it is difficult for even the most seasoned sailors to plan for a voyage and the resources needed for a successful voyage after the ship has set sail. While I may be blessed with good fortune, this good fortune will not last and only masks inefficient use of available resources. Further, a failure to plan also means that I will have failed in the first mission which is to deliver a body of work that seeks to advance research.

4) WRITING THE ESSAY

There are people blessed with a gift for words, writing, and placement of these words into a structure that elevates the work. Others are not. While I fall into the former, talent alone does not an academic researcher make. Fundamentals, structure, and discipline are essential elements. Whether writing is a natural gift or a learned behavior, Cleenewerck

& Gulma provide a framework that builds on a solid foundation for any aspiring researcher to follow (10). This begins with a wireframe in the form of an outline that will become the genesis of the draft. The draft will include three primary components – an introduction, a body where the primary points I need to make will reside, and a thrilling conclusion that summarizes the findings identified throughout (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 10). The thrilling conclusion is not solely for the end of the academic essay. Rather, each paragraph should have a definitive point, leaving the reader with a full understanding of what they should take away from what they have read that will intuitively guide them to the next paragraph, the next ideal.

5) ACHIEVING “LOGICAL FLOW”

Logical flow is a concept that deserves added emphasis. Brilliant researchers may leave their crowning academic achievement to chance if the reader is unable to follow the trail of breadcrumbs through the forest which is the essay before them. The academic writer needs to invest time and energy into making sure the ideals flow from sentence to sentence, paragraph to paragraph, and heading to heading. While this may seem trite or futile, it does allow for ideas to build organically on top of one another to weave a tapestry that all can behold, reflect on, and understand. For this reason, Cleenewerck & Gulma provide guideposts that I was able to utilize while developing my own academic essay (39). These transitive phrases allow me to interject a counterpoint forcing the reader to ponder alternate perspectives. On the other hand, I need to use this implement carefully, intentionally (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 39). As with a “choose your own adventure” story, when there are too many decision points in each section, the reader may lose track of which divergent path they are on. This may lead to frustration for the reader to retrace these steps and get back on course. This is one more indication that I, as the academic researcher, need to organize my thoughts on the proposed assignment and then craft my writing to fit within the set structure to maintain flow.

6) SIGNAL PHRASES

A key element to support the logical flow of an academic essay is the use of signal phrases. For those who are uninitiated on what signal phrases are, these are written expressions that give the academic researcher license to introduce “a quotation or paraphrase by using a verb and mentioning the author’s name” (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 38). In short, a signal phrase is a subtle art of citing without citing. Said differently, this is a writing implement that breaks with the monotony of the standard in-text citation that still gives the author credit for the idea reflected in my writing. As someone with a short attention span, the repetition of seeing multiple citations referencing the same author has a way of training my brain to ignore parts of the written text. By way of contrast, signal phrases disrupt the repetitive nature of a citation. When strategically placed throughout the academic essay, signal phrases allow the reader to remain engaged in my work while still honoring the author for their original intellectual contributions (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 38).

7) AVOIDING PLAGIARISM

Signal phrases are one method to not only give credit to the author for their intellectual contributions which help uphold the academic researcher's integrity. Why is this important? As a writer and author in my own right, I do not want someone else to take credit for my intellectual work and, in a community with others engaged in intellectual contributions, will not take credit for their works either. While Cleenewerck & Gulma take the diplomatic approach, if I would take credit, even by accident, for an author's work, my actions would constitute plagiarism (34). This is the polite way of stating that I would have committed academic fraud or intellectual piracy, offenses that come with grave consequences depending on the method, the medium, and the extent to which fraud exists. The best way to mitigate the risk of plagiarism is to give credit to the author by citing their work for contributing and furthering your research (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 34).

8) CONCLUSION

I learned a difficult lesson in writing this response paper. The first lesson is that academic essay writing is not as difficult or as daunting as I mentally built it up to be. Reading and rereading the ACA-401/ACA-401D coursepack for period 1 has aided my understanding of where to sharpen and hone my craft into well-thought-out research papers that ask a question and seek to answer the question using an evidence-based approach. Further, the coursepack provides the formula for success that will allow me to freely express my research in a way that engages the intended audience, connecting key concepts together from introduction to conclusion with summarizing statements at each transition point that leaves the reader with a morsel of information to retain when moving to the next stage of the research. Lastly, I learned to give credit to researchers and authors who came before me and contributed to my work. Crediting these authors is not only an ethical imperative, but the alternative may also prove costly to my reputation as an academic it may impact me in other ways, as well. I shall use these lessons as genesis for future research.

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. 2024. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fifth Edition. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.